

The Effect of Empowering Leadership, Job Demand, Job Crafting on Employee Performance and Well-Being as Mediation Variables

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Abstract:- This research is motivated by the refinement of previous research, in particular to analyze the effects of empowering leadership, job demand and job crafting applied to the capacity of employees with well-being which will be the mediating variable. This scientific paper uses a quantitative approach, data is collected through questionnaires distributed and observations in the company. Data processing began by distributing questionnaires to 128 employees. The data of this scientific paper was processed with the SEM-PLS (Partial Least Square) application to test and find out all the research hypotheses. Research results prove that: 1) Empowering leadership is very influential on well-being; 2) Job demand is very influential on well-being; 3) Job crafting is very influential on well-being; 4) Empowering leadership is very influential on employee performance; 5) Job demand is very influential on employee performance; 6) Job crafting is very influential on employee performance; 7) well-being is very influential on employee performance; 8) empowering leadership is very influential on employee performance mediated by well-being; 9) job demand is very influential on employee performance with well-being mediation; 10) job crafting has a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance through well-being mediation.

Originality/value: This study really fulfills several identified needs to review how employee development efforts, increase employee innovation and creativity and optimize employees to work according to their passion and how to motivate employees based on the influence of empowering leadership, job demand and job crafting on performance through wellbeing mediation.

Keywords:- Empowering Leadership, Job Demand, Job Crafting, Well-being, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources are the most important elements in an organization that provide thought, energy, talent and creativity to plan, manage and control organizational activities. The role of human resources in organizations or companies is increasingly trusted in their interests, thus encouraging a series of knowledge or theories related to how to utilize existing

individuals properly and correctly in order to achieve ideal conditions. Therefore, synergistic, good and quality performance is needed to be one of the keys for the company to survive. Performance has many influencing aspects, namely: leadership factors, individual factors, group or group factors, system factors and context factors including pressure from internal and external environmental changes, according to Mahmudi in Faturrahman, et.al (2019).

The formation of quality employees with good performance accompanied by the loyalty of the leadership or superiors of the company as the person in charge of the performance results of their subordinates. Empowering leadership can influence a variety of withdrawal behaviors (lateness, absenteeism, and turnover intentions) that leaders can control for better employee performance processes (Kim, et.al, 2017; Niko, et al, 2021; Azizi, 2019) Leaders must be able to shape employees into someone who can develop and improve themselves independently. The current job demands of employees are increasing so that it is possible for employees to experience work stress, of course this can affect organizational performance. 2021; Petrou, et. al, 2016; Tims, et. al, 2015; Robledo, et. al, 2019). The increasing demands of this job are expected for employees to have Job Crafting to re-understand their own tasks or may not have a managerial role to balance needs and work with individual skills (Tims, Bekker & Derks in Astrid Widiastuti, 2021).

Employees try to do new things leaving old ways that are considered uncertain to design their tasks so that they become more meaningful (Van, et.al, 2016). Employees try to put happiness above all else and in the workplace so that they do not expect feelings of dislike or hatred. Then this will be able to affect the results of the employee's own performance. Empowering leadership has a positive effect with psychological capital that produces greater personal and work outcomes (Kim, et.al, 2018; Niko, et.al, 2021). The ability of employees to manage emotions as a whole will affect better performance results (Park, et.al, 2017). To improve psychological well-being, management must train employees on how to deal with stress that may arise due to job demands (Ogungbamila, 2016). That the acceptance of others in terms of suggestions and feedback is critical to their well-being (Plomp, et. al, 2016; Meyers, et. al, 2017; Brandold, 2018; Passmore, 2019; Metha,

et. al, 2020; Peeters, et. al, 2016; Jalil, et. al, 2020). Job demands, such as workloads and emotional demands are unhealthy for employees' work well-being which can damage employees' psychological well-being resulting in a decline (Shah, et. al, 2017)

This study is intended to complement previous research, there is a research gap that explains empowering leadership on well-being, job demands on well-being, job crafting on well-being, empowering leadership on performance, job demands on performance, job crafting on performance, well-being on performance, well-being mediates empowering leadership on performance, well-being mediates job demands on performance, well-being mediates job crafting on performance. The purpose of this study is an important review of management and employees. In addition, it is also about understanding the variables that form the basis of performance in the organization, now and in the future.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Performance

There is a general consensus on what performance means, but different people may view it in different ways. In Sutrisno (2016) Performance is the result of the employee's perceived work process in terms of quality, quantity and working time as well as cooperation to achieve company goals. Robert Bacal in Rizki (2017) manages performance as a form of continuous communication based on partnerships between employees and direct supervisors. Realizing two-way communication is about setting clear expectations and understanding how to work together to improve performance. Armstrong and Baron in Zulkarnain (2017) performance is the result of working and facing sustainable success in an organization or business by improving employee performance through the development of group and personal abilities. Rivai in Rosmaini and Tanjung (2019), performance is the result of success with someone in a certain period of time in carrying out their responsibilities. There are seven very important performance indicators: goals and motivation. Success is determined by To achieve your goals, you need motivation. Without goals to strive for, it will be difficult to achieve this level of performance. According to Hersey in Wibowo, 2012 there are seven performance indicators, are: goals, standard, feedback, tools & facilities tools, competency, motive and opportunity.

B. Well-being

According to Ryff in Anastasia (2021), well-being is closely related to positive psychology which is referred to as psychological well-being as happiness. It allows people to have the option to acknowledge their assets and shortcomings, have positive relationships with others, control the way they behave, grow their expectations in a sustainable way, adjust to the climate and have a clear purpose in life. Ryff characterizes the elements of prosperity formulating the dimensions of well-being, namely:

➤ *Self-Acceptance*

Self-recognition is an uplifting view of oneself, both now and in the past.

➤ *Positive Relations with Others*

Positive aspects of relationships with others are the ability to form warm, satisfying social relationships, the ability to understand and trust each other, the ability to care about the welfare of others, the ability to have strong empathy, and their interactions, and the ability to give and take.

➤ *Autonomy*

Leads to independence and the ability to determine one's own destiny and regulate behavior. Independent individuals are those who can determine their own actions.

➤ *Environmental Mastery*

A person with good PWB has the skills to create and choose an environment that is suitable for psychological conditions in the context of self-development.

➤ *Purpose in Life*

A person's ability to understand the direction and purpose of his life. Individuals with life goals are good if they feel their present and past lives are useful, have the belief that they have a purpose in life and have goals to strive for in life.

➤ *Personal Growth*

It describes an individual's ability to reach his potential and grow as a good person. This dimension allows individuals to function optimally from a psychological point of view and requires self-awareness.

C. Empowering Leadership

According to Douglas L. Jones in Alexandra et.al (2016), "Empowering Leadership can be understood how managers understand their employees' behavior and motivation. This shows that leaders have the attitude and motivation to understand employees and can communicate and inspire effectively. The employees. This leadership concept also shows characteristics similar to transformational leadership and emphasizes the importance of collaboration, self-management or leadership development for every employee (Moningka, 2021. Several indicators that influence empowering leadership, are: respect, development, community and delegation.

D. Job Demand

According to Robert Karasek and Tores Teorell in Mayra Baig et.al (2018) that job demand is an example of how hard an individual or a person works (how hard you work). Job demands are things that are completed within the time available to complete many tasks, including aspects of time and speed to complete tasks. According to Karasek, job demand aspects are divided into three, namely as follows:

- a. Psychological stressor is associated with certain tasks such as workload, time pressure.

- b. Skill discretion focuses on individual or individual skills that apply to a particular job.
- c. Decision authority, a person's ability to make decisions and function correctly and effectively.

E. Crafting Jobs

According to Tims, Bakker and Derks in Robledo et.al (2019) that job crafting is an innovation when individuals/employees can take ideas to match job demands with their skills and needs, with or without management involvement. Tims et.al (2015) with job crafting employees can redesign their work with their initiative which is a strategy that employees can use to stay or engage in their work to remain valuable to the organization. Wrzesniewski & Dutton in MCW Peters et.al (2016) the job crafting process of employees is carried out in formulating and redefining their tasks (physical and cognitive) according to their tastes and desires.

Wrzesniewski and Dutton regulate the behavior of job crafting in 3 parts, namely as follows:

- Task Crafting Is changing some of the obligations or responsibilities that have been determined previously in the job description. These changes can increase or decrease tasks, change the nature of the task, change the energy and time required and give attention to other possible tasks that can be done.
- Relational Crafting This is a change in when, how, and which employees can interact with others to complete tasks. Positive interactions that exist between employees can create a sense of mutual trust and a positive attitude and vitality.
- Cognitive crafting Changes in the way employees view their work, related to tasks and all the relationships that make up work.

The hypothesis of this research is based on the theoretical study described in the literature review, the conceptual framework of the research can be described as follows:

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

- H1. X1 (Empowering Leadership) -> Y1 (Well-being)
- H2. X2 (Job Demand) -> Y1 (Well-being)
- H3. X3 (Job Crafting) -> Y1 (Well-being)
- H4. X1 (Empowering Leadership) -> Y2 (Employee Performance)
- H5. X2 (Job Demand) -> Y2 (Employee Performance)
- H6. X3 (Job Crafting) -> Y2 (Employee Performance)
- H7. Y1 (Well-being) -> Y2 (Employee Performance)
- H8. X1 (Empowering Leadership) -> Y1 (Well-being) -> Y2 (Employee Performance)
- H9. X2 (Job Demand) -> Y1 (Well-being) -> Y2 (Employee Performance)
- H10. X3 (Job Crafting) -> Y1 (Well-being) -> Y2 (Employee Performance)

III. RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODS

➤ Sample

The research was conducted at PT API Precision. The population used is the employees of PT API Precision. The sample in this study uses a non-probability sample by taking samples of all members of the population, namely 128 employees of PT API Precision.

Table 3. Variable Measurement Instruments

Variable	Dimension	Items
EL (X1)	Respect	X1.1
	Development	X1.2
	Community	X1.3
	Delegation	X1.4
JD (X2)	Psychological stressors	X2.1
	Discretion skill	X2.2
	Decision authority	X2.3
JC (X3)	Task crafting	X3.1
	Relational Crafting	X3.2
	Cognitive crafting	X3.3
WB (Y1)	Self-Acceptance	Y1.1
	Positive with Others	Y1.2
	Autonomy	Y1.3
	Environmental Mastery	Y1.4
	Purpose in Life	Y1.5
	Personal Growth	Y1.6
EP (Y2)	Goals	Y2.1
	Standard	Y2.2
	Feedback	Y2.3
	Tools	Y2.4
	Competence	Y2.5
	motive	Y2.6
	Opportunity	Y2.7
Information:		
Empowering Leadership (EL) -X1		
Job Demand (JD) - X2		
Job Crafting (JC) - X3		
Well-being (WB) - Y1		
Employee Performance (EP) - Y2		

Analysis of the data from this study using SEM PLS 3.2.8 aims to determine the direct and indirect impact of independent variables on the dependent variable. Then the researcher tested the outer model, tested the inner model and tested the hypothesis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Furthermore, table 4 shows the outer model tests, namely: Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity, Composite Reliability. Convergent validity testing is testing the validity of each construct indicator. Individual reflection measurements are considered high if the correlation is > 0.70 (Ghozali, 2014). The way to test the discriminatory validity of a reflection indicator is by looking at the cross loading between the indicator and its components/constructs. It can be used in other ways. That is comparing the square root of the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) of each construct with the correlation value between the constructs in the model. The recommended AVE value must be greater than 0.50. There are two ways to measure the reliability of a construct with reflexive indicators in the PLS SEM, namely Cronbach's omission and composite reliability.

The results of the loading factor for each indicator can be seen in the bootstrapping image below.

Fig 4.1 Bootstrapping

The test results of the image above are summarized and explained in the following table:

Table 4.1 Loading Factor Convergent Validity

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Loading Factor	Cut-off	Information
Empowering Leadership	Respect	EL_01	0.842	0.700	Valid
		EL_02	0.877		Valid
		EL_03	0.870		Valid
		EL_04	0.839		Valid
	Development	EL_05	0.863		Valid
		EL_06	0.914		Valid
		EL_07	0.886		Valid
		EL_08	0.838		Valid
	Community	EL_09	0.874		Valid
		EL_10	0.893		Valid
		EL_11	0.868		Valid
		EL_12	0.872		Valid
	Delegation	EL_13	0.834		Valid
		EL_14	0.845		Valid
		EL_15	0.880		Valid
		EL_16	0.896		Valid
Job Demand	Psychological Stressor	JD_01	0.896	Valid	
		JD_02	0.868	Valid	
		JD_03	0.858	Valid	
		JD_04	0.890	Valid	
	Skill Discretion	JD_05	0.877	Valid	
		JD_06	0.875	Valid	
		JD_07	0.833	Valid	
		JD_08	0.838	Valid	
	Decision Authority	JD_09	0.893	Valid	
		JD_10	0.899	Valid	
		JD_11	0.916	Valid	
		JD_12	0.878	Valid	
Crafting Jobs	Task Crafting	JC_01	0.891	Valid	
		JC_02	0.903	Valid	
		JC_03	0.879	Valid	
		JC_04	0.872	Valid	
	Relational Crafting	JC_05	0.874	Valid	
		JC_06	0.856	Valid	
		JC_07	0.906	Valid	
		JC_08	0.923	Valid	
	Cognitive Crafting	JC_09	0.901	Valid	
		JC_10	0.885	Valid	
		JC_11	0.878	Valid	
		JC_12	0.934	Valid	
Well-being	Self-Acceptance	WB_01	0.923	Valid	
		WB_02	0.934	Valid	
		WB_03	0.873	Valid	
	Positive Relations With Others	WB_04	0.850	Valid	
		WB_05	0.944	Valid	
		WB_06	0.913	Valid	
	Autonomy	WB_07	0.927	Valid	
		WB_08	0.936	Valid	
		WB_09	0.911	Valid	
	Environmental Mastery	WB_10	0.888	Valid	

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Loading Factor	Cut-off	Information
	<i>Purpose in life</i>	WB_11	0.901		Valid
		WB_12	0.914		Valid
		WB_13	0.904		Valid
		WB_14	0.922		Valid
		WB_15	0.918		Valid
	<i>Personal Growth</i>	WB_16	0.951		Valid
		WB_17	0.943		Valid
		WB_18	0.947		Valid
<i>Employee Performance</i>	<i>Goals</i>	EP_01	0.945		Valid
		EP_02	0.947		Valid
	<i>Standard</i>	EP_03	0.941		Valid
		EP_04	0.944		Valid
	<i>Feedback</i>	EP_05	0.934		Valid
		EP_06	0.932		Valid
	<i>Tools</i>	EP_07	0.905		Valid
		EP_08	0.899		Valid
		EP_09	0.911	Valid	
	<i>Competence</i>	EP_10	0.914	Valid	
		EP_11	0.914	Valid	
		EP_12	0.922	Valid	
	<i>motive</i>	EP_13	0.958	Valid	
		EP_14	0.960	Valid	
	<i>Opportunity</i>	EP_15	0.936	Valid	
		EP_16	0.935	Valid	

From the table above it can be seen that The overall loading factor of the second order CFA shows that the model has met the convergent validity requirements because the loading factor value is more than 0.7. This means that all indicators are valid as a measuring tool for their respective variables on all research variables, namely empowering leadership, job demand, job crafting, well-being, and employee performance.

Table 4.2 Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for Discriminant Validity

Variables and Dimensions	AVE	Stress
X1 (Empowering Leadership)	0.655	Valid
X1.1 (Respect)	0.735	Valid
X1.2 (Development)	0.767	Valid
X1.3 (Community)	0.769	Valid
X1.4 (Delegation)	0.747	Valid
X2 (Job Demand)	0.634	Valid
X2.1 (Psychological Stressor)	0.771	Valid
X2.2 (Skill Discretion)	0.732	Valid
X2.3 (Decision Authority)	0.804	Valid
X3 (Job Crafting)	0.694	Valid
X3.1 (Task Crafting)	0.785	Valid
X3.2 (Relational Crafting)	0.792	Valid
X3.3 (Cognitive Crafting)	0.810	Valid
Y1 (Well-being)	0.755	Valid
Y1.1 (Self-Acceptance)	0.829	Valid
Y1.2 (Positive Relations With Others)	0.815	Valid
Y1.3 (Autonomy)	0.855	Valid
Y1.4 (Environmental Mastery)	0.812	Valid
Y1.5 (Purpose In Life)	0.837	Valid
Y1.6 (Personal Growth)	0.897	Valid
Y2 (Employee Performance)	0.708	Valid

Variables and Dimensions	AVE	Stress
Y2.1 (Goals)	0.894	Valid
Y2.2 (Standard)	0.888	Valid
Y2.3 (Feedback)	0.870	Valid
Y2.4 (Tools)	0.819	Valid
Y2.5 (Competence)	0.840	Valid
Y2.6 (Motive)	0.919	Valid
Y2.7 (Opportunity)	0.875	Valid

From the table above it can be seen that all AVE values > 0.5. This shows that all latent variables in the estimated model meet the convergent validity (valid) criteria.

Table 4 .3 Fornell-Lacker for Discriminant Validity

	X1	X2	X3	Y1	Y2
X1	0.809				
X2	0.665	0.796			
X3	0.742	0.619	0.833		
Y1	0.756	0.663	0.722	0.869	
Y2	0.807	0.741	0.768	0.833	0.842

From the table above seen in the value of the square root of the AVE and the correlation value between latent variables (constructs) with other constructs shows a greater value. It can be concluded very well that the consequences of assessing discriminant legitimacy through the Fornell-Lacker standard for inert development as a whole have a valid discriminant legitimacy score.

Table 4.4 Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha

Variables and Dimensions	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Information
X1 (Empowering Leadership)	0.965	0.968	Reliable
X1.1 (Respect)	0.879	0.917	Reliable
X1.2 (Development)	0.898	0.929	Reliable
X1.3 (Community)	0.900	0.930	Reliable
X1.4 (Delegation)	0.887	0.922	Reliable
X2 (Job Demand)	0.947	0.954	Reliable
X2.1 (Psychological Stressor)	0.901	0.931	Reliable
X2.2 (Skill Discretion)	0.878	0.916	Reliable
X2.3 (Decision Authority)	0.919	0.943	Reliable
X3 (Job Crafting)	0.960	0.965	Reliable
X3.1 (Task Crafting)	0.909	0.936	Reliable
X3.2 (Relational Crafting)	0.912	0.938	Reliable
X3.3 (Cognitive Crafting)	0.921	0.944	Reliable
Y1 (Well-being)	0.981	0.982	Reliable
Y1.1 (Self-Acceptance)	0.896	0.936	Reliable
Y1.2 (Positive Relations With Others)	0.886	0.930	Reliable
Y1.3 (Autonomy)	0.915	0.947	Reliable
Y1.4 (Environmental Mastery)	0.884	0.928	Reliable
Y1.5 (Purpose In Life)	0.903	0.939	Reliable
Y1.6 (Personal Growth)	0.943	0.963	Reliable
Y2 (Employee Performance)	0.972	0.975	Reliable
Y2.1 (Goals)	0.882	0.944	Reliable
Y2.2 (Standard)	0.874	0.941	Reliable
Y2.3 (Feedback)	0.851	0.931	Reliable
Y2.4 (Tools)	0.890	0.931	Reliable
Y2.5 (Competence)	0.905	0.940	Reliable

Variables and Dimensions	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Information
Y2.6 (Motive)	0.912	0.958	Reliable
Y2.7 (Opportunity)	0.857	0.933	Reliable

From the table aboveshow Composite Reliability and Cronbachs Alpha values for all latent variables above > 0.70. Therefore, all manifest variables are declared reliable when measuring the latent variables of the estimation model.

Table 4.5 Structural Model Evaluation

Endogenous Variable (Construct)	R Square	Information
Y1 (Well-being)	0.655	Strong
Y2 (Employee Performance)	0.810	Strong

Table above shows a well-being value of 0.655, the value is between 0.50 and 0.75, this resultclassified as strong, these results explain that 65.5% well-beinginfluenced by empowering leadership, job demand and job crafting, the remaining 34.5% was influenced by other factors not observed in this study. While the second R2 value of 0.810 is above 0.75 which is quite strong, these results explain that 81% of employee performance is influenced by empowering leadership, job demand, job crafting, and well-being, while the remaining 19% is influenced by other factors not studied. in this research.

Table 4.6 Overall Model Fit

Variable	AVE	R Square
X1 (Empowering Leadership)	0.655	-
X2 (Job Demand)	0.634	-
X3 (Job Crafting)	0.694	-
Y1 (Well-being)	0.755	0.655
Y2 (Employee Performance)	0.708	0.810
Average	0.689	0.732
GoF Value (According to Formula)	0.710	
Conclusion	Large GoF value (Model Fit)	

In the table aboveit can be seen that the overall suitability value for the model is 0.710. This shows that the model formed in this study as a whole has a strong predictive power, namely the model meets the goodness of fit criteria.

Table 7 shows the hypothesis test, to test the hypothesis by using statistical values, then for alpha 5% the t-statistic value is 1.96. Therefore, the criteria for accepting/rejecting a hypothesis are that Ha will be accepted and H0 will be rejected if the t-statistic > 1.96. To reject/accept the hypothesis using probability then Ha is accepted if the p value <0.05. If the significance value of t < 0.05, then H0 is rejected, meaning that the dependent variable is strongly influenced by the independent variable. If the significance of t > 0.05, then H0 is accepted. This means that there is no significant effect between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table 4.7 Direct Effect and Indirect Effect Hypothesis Test

Variable	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values	Information
Direct Effect				
X1 (Empowering Leadership) -> Y1 (Well-being)	0.390	3,840	0.000	Significant
X2 (Job Demand) -> Y1 (Well-being)	0.219	2,170	0.030	Significant
X3 (Job Crafting) -> Y1 (Well-being)	0.298	2,416	0.016	Significant
X1 (Empowering Leadership) -> Y2 (Employee Performance)	0.245	2,344	0.019	Significant
X2 (Job Demand) -> Y2 (Employee Performance)	0.219	2,120	0.035	Significant
X3 (Job Crafting) -> Y2 (Employee Performance)	0.183	2,321	0.021	Significant
Y1 (Well-being) -> Y2 (Employee Performance)	0.370	3,199	0.001	Significant
Indirect Effect (Indirect Effect)				
X1 (Empowering Leadership) -> Y1 (Well-being) -> Y2 (Employee Performance)	0.144	2,140	0.033	Significant
X2 (Job Demand) -> Y1 (Well-being) -> Y2 (Employee Performance)	0.081	1,985	0.048	Significant
X3 (Job Crafting) -> Y1 (Well-being) -> Y2 (Employee Performance)	0.110	1,669	0.096	Not Significant

V. DISCUSSION

A. *The Effect of Empowering Leadership on Well-being*

From the hypothesis test in table 4.7, path coefficient value of 0.390 significant at t-statistic $3.840 > t\text{-table } 1.96$ and at p-value $0.000 < 0.05$ significance level. Thus, the hypothesis can be accepted that there is a positive and significant effect of empowering leadership on well-being. Withdrawal behavior can be controlled if the leader can strengthen his followers or employees through emotional ties with the organization by offering the support, guidance and opportunities needed to participate in the work process (Kim, et al., 2018). Empowering leadership must directly generate trust because empowering leadership includes relational oriented behavior,

B. *Effect of Job Demand on Well-being*

The test results in table 7, shows the path coefficient value of 0.219 is significant at t-statistic $2.170 > t\text{-table } 1.96$ and at P-value $0.030 < 0.05$ significance level. The increasing demands of work faced by employees, this increases the interest of employees to learn new things to be applied to their respective jobs so that they can lighten the workload and have a healthy and balanced work life. Time pressure causes physiological and psychological stress for employees which results in employees losing control at work if the organization does not pay attention to it (Adil, et al., 2018)

C. *The Effect of Job Crafting on Well-being*

The test results in table 7 show the path coefficient value of 0.298 significant at t-statistic $2.416 > t\text{-table } 1.96$ and at p-value $0.016 < 0.05$ significance level. Employees can delegate tasks well and establish positive interactions with employees with or without leadership involvement to balance work demands with their abilities and needs. Job crafting is a global concept that is triggered by a positive state of mind (involvement) and not by negative states of mind such as emotional exhaustion and workaholism (Robledo, et al., 2019). Job crafting positively affects well being, a positive correlation between job crafting and a person's satisfaction will increase his or her well being (Niko, et al., 2021). That social support resources / employees who decline will affect employee welfare. Conversely, if employee social support is high, it will increase employee welfare (Mehta, et al., 2021).

D. *The Effect of Empowering Leadership on Employee Performance*

The test results in table 7 show the path coefficient value of 0.245 is significant at t-statistic $2.344 > t\text{-table } 1.96$ and at p-value $0.019 < 0.05$ significance level. Thus, the hypothesis can be accepted that there is a positive and significant effect of empowering leadership on employee performance. Positive behavior at work, discipline, obeying rules and being responsible for their work is evidence of the influence of empowering leadership on employee performance (Niko, et al., 2021). The positive effect of empowering leadership on employee performance is that employee performance is a broad concept that involves subordinates in decision making and gives

them autonomy and freedom to manage their work (Kim, et al., 2018).

E. *Job Demand Against Employee Performance*

The test results in table 7, shows the path coefficient value of 0.219 is significant at t-statistic $2.120 > t\text{-table } 1.96$ and at P-value $0.035 < 0.05$ significance level. Thus the hypothesis can be accepted that there is a significant effect of job demand on employee performance. The level of employee learning demands is negatively related to job performance and job satisfaction. It is important to use the potential of reducing learning demands and increasing work engagement to improve employee performance (Mikkelsen, et al., 2017). Job demand has a negative impact on employee performance, job demand experienced by employees can trigger employees to implement their abilities, .

F. *The Effect of Job Crafting on Employee Performance*

The test results in table 7, shows the path coefficient value of 0.183 is significant at t-statistic $2.321 > t\text{-table } 1.96$ and at p-value $0.021 < 0.05$ significance level. Thus the hypothesis can be accepted that there is a positive and significant effect of job crafting on employee performance. Job crafting can be a promising way to keep employees excited at work, improve their careers and commitments as well as their well-being that affects career success and career commitment (Kim, et al., 2018). The role of human resource practices in encouraging employee performance in job crafting is to design their work with more roles so as to improve the performance of the employees themselves (Guan, et al., 2018).

G. *Effect of Well-being on Employee Performance*

The test results in table 7, shows the path coefficient value of 0.370 was significant at t-statistic $3.199 > t\text{-table } 1.96$ and at p-value $0.001 < 0.05$ significance level. Thus the hypothesis can be. Good Psychological Capital development by individuals will lead to an increase in employee performance. This will result in greater benefits for the organization through rewards given to employees where employees get the opportunity to develop and use their strengths or abilities (Woerkom, et al., 2017). Wellbeing has a positive impact on encouraging employee performance outcomes in the organization,

H. *Influence Empowering Leadership Against Employee Performance Mediated By Well-being*

The test results in table 7 show the path coefficient value or the results of the mediation effect test regarding the effect of *empowering leadership* on employee performance mediated by well-being of 0.144, obtained t-statistics value of 2.140 and p-value of 0.033, these results indicate that t-statistics value $> t\text{-table } 1.96$ and p-value $< \text{significance level } 0, 05$. Thus, the hypothesis can be accepted that there is a positive and significant effect of empowering leadership on employee performance mediated by well-being. Leaders who give freedom or autonomy in decision-making to employees this will help employees to understand the importance of the work being done and employees will experience a better level of

psychological empowerment (Kundu, et al., 2019). Employee awareness / mindfulness can be used as a positive tool to improve employee performance in the organization (Passmore, 2019).

I. Influence Job Demand Against Employee Performance Mediated By Well-being

The test results in table 7 show the path coefficient value or the results of the mediation effect test regarding the effect of *job demand* on employee performance mediated by well-being of 0.081, obtained a t-statistics value of 1.985 and a p-value of 0.048. These results indicate that the t-statistics value > t-table 1.96 and p-value < 0.05 significance level. Thus the hypothesis can be accepted that there is a positive and significant effect of job demand on employee performance mediated by well-being. Job demand is a job or task that requires physical and psychological effort from workers that creates tension or stress on employees. This means that if workers can balance work demands with positive thoughts through worker wellbeing, this can affect employee performance (Niks, et al., 2018). Wellbeing has a positive impact on employees to encourage employee performance results and has a positive relationship with work performance in the organization (Silvina, 2018). Job demands such as workload and emotional demands are not good for the welfare of employees, resulting in a decrease for employees (Asif, et al., 2017).

J. Influence Crafting Jobs Against Employee Performance Mediated By Well-being

The test results in table 7 show the path coefficient value or the results of the mediation effect test regarding the effect of *crafting* on employee performance mediated by well-being of 0.110 obtained t-statistics value of 1.669 and p-value of 0.096, these results indicate that the value of t-statistics < t-table 1.96 and p-value > 0.05 significance level. Thus the hypothesis is rejected that there is a positive and insignificant effect of job crafting on employee performance mediated by well-being. Based on the smallest loading factor in WB-04 of 0.850, employees lack empathy for other people with different backgrounds. Companies need to increase motivation for employees through the leaders of each division to provide direction by placing themselves as other people in order to get out of each employee's comfort zone. These results are not in line with research (Niko, et.al, 2021) Job crafting can increase worker competence, the desire to learn and develop as well as persistence to refer to the future era will positively affect the achievement of goals. That someone with positive goals will feel that life is more meaningful and more vibrant which results in more productive workers and able to handle heavier workloads.

VI. CONCLUSION

It is known that there is a direct and significant influence between empowering leadership and wellbeing. Then the pioneer can open the door for workers to learn through the preparation and progress made by the organization and properly implemented by the representatives and the organization for better improvement. Job demand is very influential on wellbeing. This means that employees innovate and create their own creativity and new ways to complete tasks well. The better the application of job demand with the decision authority approach in terms of achieving employee wellbeing at the company will support better improvements. Job crafting is very influential on wellbeing. This means that employees establish good communication with all parties, both internal and external to the company.

Empowering leadership is very influential on employee performance. The better the application of empowering leadership with a development approach to employees and providing rewards for employees who excel will motivate employees to work. Job demand is very influential on employee performance. This means that employees innovate and create their own creativity and new ways to complete tasks well. The better application of job demand with the decision authority approach will motivate employees and improve employee performance. Job crafting is very influential on employee performance. This means that employees establish good communication with all parties, both internal and external to the company. The better the implementation of employee job crafting in terms of relational crafting will motivate employees to improve performance. Wellbeing is very influential on employee performance. This means that employees have an open attitude to new knowledge and experiences. The better the application of wellbeing in terms of personal growth will motivate employees to improve performance.

Empowering leadership is very influential on employee performance through mediation of wellbeing. This means that learning opportunities through appropriate development for employees will be more effective in promoting better improvements within the company to motivate employees to improve individual performance. Job demand is very influential on employee performance through the mediation of wellbeing. The better the application of job demand with the appropriate decision authority approach to employees, the more effective it will be to motivate employees to improve individual performance. Job crafting has no significant effect on employee performance through the mediation of wellbeing.

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